

EFFECT OF CASSIA OCCIDENTALIS ON BIOCHEMICAL PARAMETERS OF SECOND-DEGREE BURN WOUNDS IN WISTAR STRAIN RATS

Koudou Dago Désiré^{1,2*}, Soro Silyibe^{1,2}, Koffi Allali Eugène^{1,2}, Gbogbo Moussa^{1,2}, Okou Obou Constantin^{1,2}

¹Training and Research Unit of Agroforestry, Laboratory of Agro valorization, University Jean Lorougnon Guédé, PO Box 150, Daloa, Côte d'Ivoire.

²Group of Excellence for Research on Traditional Pharmacopoeia Products, University Jean Lorougnon Guédé, PO Box 150, Daloa, Côte d'Ivoire.

Article Received on
29 July 2025,

Revised on 19 August 2025,
Accepted on 08 Sept. 2025,

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17213926>

***Corresponding Author**

Koudou Dago Désiré

Training and Research Unit
of Agroforestry, Laboratory
of agro Valorization,
University Jean Lorougnon
Guédé, PO Box 150, Daloa,
Côte d'Ivoire.

ABSTRACT

Cassia occidentalis, also known as false kinkeliba, is a medicinal plant known for its therapeutic properties. The objective of this study was to demonstrate its effects on certain biochemical parameters of wound healing in a model of second-degree experimental burns in Wistar rats. These burn wounds were treated with *C. occidentalis* leaf extract at doses of 125, 250, and 500 mg/kg, respectively, and concentrations of 40 and 80 mg/ml, and flukocin, a benchmark molecule for wound healing. The results of this work indicate certain pathways or mechanisms of pharmacological action that can support the healing effects of *C. occidentalis*. The 500 mg/kg extract promotes healing by reconstituting the skin layer. This healing process could be explained by the presence in the leaves of this plant of flavonoids, polyphenols, sterols and poly terpenes, alkaloids and saponosides contained in these leaves.

KEYWORDS: *C. occidentalis*, biochemical parameters, burn, Wistar rat.

INTRODUCTION

A burn is a destruction of the skin covering and underlying tissues caused by various thermal, chemical, or radiation agents (Plancq et al., 2016). The resulting inflammatory reaction is a

defense mechanism, but it can become excessive and harmful. It is characterized by cell injury, tissue destruction, secretion of pro-inflammatory mediators (TNF- α ,) and production by neutrophils of reactive oxygen species (ROS) (Kassasseya *et al.*, 2024). These reactive oxygen species amplify inflammation by attacking the double bonds of membrane fatty acids to generate toxic lipid radicals such as malondialdehyde (MDA) (Antonio *et al.*, 2014) and (Mason *et al.*, 2016). This vicious cycle delays healing and increases the risk of fibrosis or infection. The resulting wounds can pose complex therapeutic challenges as their healing is a dynamic, coordinated process involving cell multiplication, active cell migration, and extracellular matrix production (Yue *et al.*, 2014). In Africa, faced with the problem of costs and/or accessibility of therapeutic care, populations are increasingly turning to traditional pharmacies and traditional practitioners as an alternative to conventional treatment (WHO, 2019). In Ivory Coast, the flora contains plants with healing activity. Many studies have shown the healing activity of some of these medicinal plants such as *Tetrapleura tetraptera* (Tsala *et al.*, 2014) and *Kalanchoe crenata* (Djoko *et al.*, 2016). *Cassia occidentalis* called false Kinkeliba is a plant whose leaves are used in the preparation of several remedies commonly used to relieve a wide variety of ailments including wound healing (AKÉ, 1983). Recent studies have shown the effectiveness of aqueous extract of *Cassia occidentalis* on second-degree burn wounds in rats (Soro *et al.*, 2025). However, the biochemical mechanisms underlying this healing activity remain little explored scientifically. This study therefore aims to highlight the effects of *Cassia occidentalis* on the biochemical parameters of burn wounds through an experimental evaluation, in order to validate its traditional use and to open the way to a pharmacological valorization of this endogenous plant.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Plant Material

The plant material consisted of *Cassia occidentalis* leaves. They were harvested in the Daloa region in west-central Côte d'Ivoire.

Animals

The experiments used 180- to 220-gram rats of the *Rattus norvegicus* species, Wistar strain, from the laboratory at the Félix Houphouët-Boigny University in Cocody. They were placed in individual plastic cages with a mesh lid and provided with baby bottles. A layer of wood shavings was placed at the bottom of the cages to constitute the bedding. They were fed daily with pellets from the company IVOGRAIN and tap water in the baby bottles.

Methods

1 Preparation of the Total Aqueous Extract

Harvested *Cassia occidentalis* leaves were washed and then dried away from light at room temperature (25-30°C) for three weeks in the Biochemistry Laboratory of Jean Lorougnon Guédé University. They were then ground into powder using an electric grinder (Retsch sk 100). The powder obtained was macerated according to the method of **Zirihi et al. (2003)**, one hundred grams (150g) of *Cassia occidentalis* powder were put in one and a half liters of distilled water. The mixture was homogenized 10 times at a rate of 2 minutes per revolution using a Binatone brand mixer. The homogenate obtained was wrung out in a square of white cotton cloth and then filtered three times through absorbent cotton and once through Whatman paper (3 mm). The filtrate was evaporated at 50°C using a venticelle® type oven.

2 Wound Induction

Rats were anesthetized by inhalation in a bell jar containing cotton soaked in ethyl ether for 2 to 3 minutes. Their dorsal flanks were shaved and cleaned with 70° surgical alcohol, 24 hours before burn induction. Experimental burns were induced using a 3 cm diameter metal cylinder connected to a rod with a handle. The cylinder heated to a temperature of 200 °C is applied for 20 seconds by pressing lightly on the surface of the shaved skin of the rats in order to cause extensive deep second-degree burns (**Masson et al., 2020**). This burn is characterized by damage to the epidermis and dermis with the presence of phlyctenae (liquid of vascular origin forming a bubble which develops at the epidermis-dermis interface) with a red background, whitish areas.

3 Force-feeding the rats

The twenty-five (25) rats divided into five (05) groups were treated according to the method of **Soro et al., (2025)**.

- The rats in group 1 were treated with distilled water (control rats).
- The rats in group 2 were treated with the plant extract at a dose of 125 mg/kg with a concentration of 40 mg/ml.
- The rats in group 3 were treated with the plant extract at a dose of 250 mg/kg with a concentration of 40 mg/ml.
- The rats in group 4 were treated with the plant extract at a dose of 500 mg/kg with a concentration of 80 mg/ml.

-The rats in group 5 were treated with Flukocin 500 at a dose of 25 mg/kg with a concentration of 6.66 mg/ml. All of these rats were assessed daily for twenty-eight days after wound induction.

4 Biochemical Marker Assays

Inflammation, systemic oxidative stress, matrix remodeling and antioxidant capacity were respectively assessed at Day 0, Day 1, Day 3, Day 7, Day 14, Day 21 and Day 28 by measuring the levels of tumor necrosis factor alpha (TNF- α) (Sun *et al.*, 2012), malondialdehyde (MDA) (Rao *et al.*, 2021), hydroxyproline (Qiu B, *et al.*, 2014) as well as superoxide dismutase (SOD) activity (Ramasarma *et al.*, 2015).

5 Statistical Analysis

Results are expressed as means plus or minus standard errors of the mean ($M \pm SEM$). Means between treated and control groups were compared using the Student t-test. The significance threshold was set at $p < 0.05$.

RESULTS

Serum levels of biochemical markers

TNF- α and MDA levels increased sharply from the onset of wounds and then decreased in all groups, especially significantly in groups 4 and 5, tending towards baseline values over the following weeks **Tables 1 & 2**. However, SOD activity evolved in the opposite direction. The acute inflammatory peak occurred on D₁, followed by gradual normalization from Day 7 **Table 3** Hydroxyproline levels gradually increased, reaching a peak on Day 14 and then falling towards baseline values at the end of treatment **Tale 4**.

Table 1: TNF- α levels (pg/mL) in different batches over time.

	Distilled water	Extract (125 mg/kg)	Extract (250 mg/kg)	Extract (500 mg/kg)	Flukocin 500 (25 mg/kg)
D ₀	17,5 \pm 1,8	14,1 \pm 1,9	15 \pm 1,2	15 \pm 1,6	15,4 \pm 1,84
D ₀₁	190,2 \pm 10,16	183 \pm 6,8	174,6 \pm 13,68	123,8 \pm 7,44*	119,4 \pm 4,48
D ₀₃	184,8 \pm 5,36	143,68 \pm 5,58	132 \pm 9,6	81,18 \pm 12,10**	80 \pm 7,92
D ₀₇	132,6 \pm 13,04	114 \pm 7,2	63,2 \pm 11,68	65,2 \pm 3,68	47 \pm 8,4
D ₁₄	82,6 \pm 7,52	68 \pm 9,6	38,1 \pm 3,12	35 \pm 5,2	30 \pm 3,2
D ₂₁	64,6 \pm 5,68	47,4 \pm 2,88	26 \pm 3,2	21,4 \pm 1,92	20 \pm 2,8
D ₂₈	32 \pm 4,8	19,8 \pm 2,16	16,2 \pm 1,04	12,5 \pm 1,4	13,1 \pm 0,8

Results are expressed as mean ($M \pm SEM$). * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$ compared to control

Table 2: MDA levels (ng/mL) in different batches as a function of time.

	Distilled water	Extract (125 mg/kg)	Extract (250 mg/kg)	Extract (500 mg/kg)	Flukocin 500 (25 mg/kg)
D ₀	12,31 ± 1,77	13,4 ± 2,48	10,09 ± 1,76	10,09 ± 1,76	10,5 ± 1,4
D ₀₁	69,6 ± 5,12	77,2 ± 10,24	48,6 ± 3,92	36,2 ± 4***	37,6 ± 6,08
D ₀₃	92,6 ± 4,32	91,2 ± 3,04	58,04 ± 4,60***	49,12 ± 4,78	51,6 ± 3,12
D ₀₇	84,6 ± 2,88	67,6 ± 4,72	43,3 ± 2,36	34,4 ± 5,8	26,2 ± 2,64
D ₁₄	66,6 ± 4,32	55,6 ± 6,72	26,28 ± 11,01	19,48 ± 2,65	16,2 ± 2,16
D ₂₁	42,2 ± 5,44	39,2 ± 3,92	18,78 ± 3,53	13,32 ± 0,94	11,21 ± 1,03
D ₂₈	26,2 ± 1,04	24,8 ± 1,12	11,56 ± 0,72	11,52 ± 0,57***	12,6 ± 1,92

Results are expressed as mean (M ± SEM). * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$ compared to control

Table 3: SOD activities (ng/mL) in different batches as a function of time.

	Distilled water	Extract (125 mg/kg)	Extract (250 mg/kg)	Extract (500 mg/kg)	Flukocin 500 (25 mg/kg)
D ₀	146 ± 10	144,6 ± 9,12	187,8 ± 4,56	206,2 ± 3,84	187,8 ± 4,56
D ₀₁	126 ± 6	119 ± 8	178 ± 2,4	196 ± 2	178 ± 2,4
D ₀₃	87,2 ± 13,04	89,6 ± 3,92	97,4 ± 1,12	99,4 ± 1,28	95,4 ± 2,72
D ₀₇	78,6 ± 1,44	104,6 ± 3,92*	118 ± 10,4**	166,8 ± 1,44***	145,4 ± 8,32***
D ₁₄	97,2 ± 6,16	118 ± 3,12	136,2 ± 4,64	177,6 ± 3,44	154 ± 6,72
D ₂₁	113 ± 1,6	123,4 ± 3,68	145,8 ± 4,64	185 ± 3,6	167,6 ± 1,52
D ₂₈	131,8 ± 2,5	127 ± 4,4	159 ± 5,2	190,8 ± 4,56	183,2 ± 4,72

Results are expressed as mean (M ± SEM). * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$ compared to control

Table 4: Hydroxyproline levels (µg/mL) in different batches over time.

	Distilled water	Extract (125 mg/kg)	Extract (250 mg/kg)	Extract (500 mg/kg)	Flukocin 500 (25 mg/kg)
D ₀	6,2 ± 2,16	6,2 ± 2,16	4,2 ± 1,36	4,4 ± 1,52	5 ± 0,8
D ₀₁	4,2 ± 1,36	5 ± 2	11 ± 1,2	12,4 ± 1,92	12,4 ± 1,9
D ₀₃	6,2 ± 1,04	6,8 ± 1,36	22,8 ± 1,84	40 ± 8	31,6 ± 2,08
D ₀₇	7,8 ± 1,36	9 ± 1,2	36,2 ± 3,28	68,4 ± 8,48	61,2 ± 2,96
D ₁₄	9,8 ± 0,64	10,6 ± 1,12	42,8 ± 1,76	87,6 ± 7,52	73,8 ± 2,64
D ₂₁	5,8 ± 0,64	6,6 ± 1,12	17,6 ± 4,08	53,8 ± 6,56	44,2 ± 3,04
D ₂₈	4,6 ± 1,52	5,4 ± 1,28	11,6 ± 0,88	16,4 ± 3,28	15,6 ± 2,32

Results are expressed as mean (M ± SEM). * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$ compared to control

DISCUSSION

Our results indicate that from the first days of wound induction, TNF- α and MDA levels increase in synergy with the decrease in SOD activities in all groups, up to Day 7. We thus observe a concomitant inflammatory response causing the release of excess reactive oxygen species that destroy molecules and cells (Kassaseya *et al.*, 2024), (Ravat *et al.*, 2011), lipid peroxidation of cell membranes (Yin *et al.*, 2011) and depletion of antioxidant defenses (Sies *et al.*, 2015). These results obtained could be explained by the fact that the action of the

extract is not immediate and instantaneous from the first days. Subsequently, these observed effects were effectively and progressively attenuated by the aqueous extract of the leaves of *C. Occidentalis* from Day 7. Indeed, after two weeks of treatment, the results show an increase in superoxide dismutase (SOD) activities correlated with a decrease in TNF- α and MDA levels. This result suggests an antioxidant defense (**Birben et al., 2012**), an anti-inflammatory effect (**Fernandes et al., 2007**) and a reduction of oxidative stress (**Birben et al., 2012**) promoting better tissue repair. These different effects would be due to the actions of saponosides, polyphenols and flavonoids present in the aqueous extract of *C. occidentalis* leaves as indicated by **Soro et al. (2025)**. The extract could either have a direct antioxidant effect by scavenging reactive oxygen species or by acting via the stimulation of endogenous SOD synthesis (**Kruk et al., 2017**). The high-dose extract limits lipid damage. This result is similar to that of **Ayala et al., (2014)**. Finally, the progressive increase up to Day 14 in the level of Hydroxyproline could reflect the active synthesis of collagen. Indeed, according to **Carvalho et al., (2021)**, the healing action of this plant would involve the stimulation of the production of fibroblasts and/or collagen fibers or a stimulation of angiogenesis. The presence of flavonoids in the aqueous extract of *C. occidentalis* leaves would contribute to this active synthesis of collagen (**Soro et al. 2025**). On the other hand, the decrease observed after Day 21 could correspond to a remodeling and degradation of immature collagen as described **Rozario et al., 2010**).

Conclusion and Outlook

The results of this study demonstrated that *C. occidentalis* leaf extract possesses healing properties commonly used in traditional medicine. It also identified certain pharmacological pathways or mechanisms of action that may support the healing effects of *C. occidentalis*. The 500 mg/kg extract is the most promising, combining rapid and prolonged anti-inflammatory and antioxidant action. This study contributes to the overall promotion of plant biodiversity and the improvement of health for better sustainable development.

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